

Path to Competitive Success Internationally Through Supply Chain Management: The Case of L'Oréal

**Danita Doxa Widiyanto
Lena Ellitan**

lena@ukwms.ac.id

Faculty of Business, Widya Mandala Catholic University Surabaya, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

The supply chain in any business is made up of all the operations required to fulfill orders from customers. This includes the transfer of goods in both ways as well as information, assets, and goods from suppliers to manufacturers to distributors. L'Oréal, a market leader in the cosmetic industry, has gained a competitive advantage by efficiently managing its global supply chain. Integrating digital technologies makes simpler to come up with innovative approaches to challenges facing society. One such example is the use of data analytics to recognize social needs, produce sustainable goods, and improve community well-being. Sustainable practices, supplier collaboration, and customer-centric strategies ensure product quality and safety while meeting environmental and social considerations will improve customer satisfaction. L'Oréal also embraces technology and innovation, collaborating with startups and technology partners to continuously improve its supply chain processes. By addressing cybersecurity risks and skilled workforce, L'Oréal anticipates future trends and disruptions in supply chain management, positioning itself for sustained international success. The purpose of this paper are: (1). To understand how L'Oréal manage to deal with its globalization and digital expansion. (2). To know how L'Oréal implements the distribution network and applications to online sales. (3). To understand ways to improve the supply chain coordination of L'Oréal. (4). The understand the transformation process of L'Oréal's supply chain system. (5). To analyze L'Oréal's supply chain strategy by integrating technology and data-driven practices.

Key words: Supply chain management, supply chain processes, competitive advantage, L'Oréal.

INTRODUCTION

L'Oréal's global presence is a key aspect of its international competitive success. With operations in over 150 countries, L'Oréal has reached a wide customer base and diverse markets. For the fifth consecutive year, L'Oréal has been recognized by Gartner as a top Supply Chain firm because of its success in sustainability, digital transformation, and agility.

In the 2023 Gartner Worldwide Supply Chain rating, L'Oréal came in at rank 10 (Gartner, 2023). This shows that up to this year the supply chain management plays a crucial role in L'Oréal's international competitiveness and ensuring efficient operations. The effective management of the supply chain allows L'Oréal to streamline its processes, optimize inventory management, and enhance operational efficiency. The company's digital supply chain transformation has also further enhanced its capabilities in this area, enabling the implementation of digital technologies and data analytics for improved decision-making and forecasting.

L'Oréal, a market leader in the cosmetic industry, has gained a competitive advantage by efficiently managing its global supply chain. Integrating digital technologies makes simpler to come up with innovative approaches to challenges facing society. One such example is the use of data analytics to recognize social needs, produce sustainable goods, and improve community well-being (Martínez-Peláez, R. et al, 2023). Sustainable practices, supplier collaboration, and customer-centric strategies ensure product quality and safety while meeting environmental and social considerations will improve customer satisfaction. L'Oréal also embraces technology and innovation, collaborating with startups and technology partners to continuously improve its supply chain processes. By addressing cybersecurity risks and skilled workforce, L'Oréal anticipates future trends and disruptions in supply chain management, positioning itself for sustained international success.

Howarth, J. (2023). The Ultimate List of Beauty Industry Stats (2023). <https://explodingtopics.com/blog/beauty-industry-stats>

The data presented in the Figure 1 graph below indicates that L'Oréal's Western Europe zone generated a total of roughly 7.5 billion euros in 2020. Based on compiled number of zones, including Latin America, North and South America, the Pacific, the Middle East, North and Sub-Saharan Africa, and the Middle East. This indicates that this area saw the biggest increase in sales, indicating that there is potential growth in the future. Despite the fact that

the data indicates that new markets are growing at the fastest rate.

Consolidated sales of L'Oréal worldwide from 2010 to 2020, by geographic zone
(in million euros)

Source: Petruzzi, D. (2021). Consolidated sales of L'Oréal worldwide from 2010 to 2020, by geographic zone. Statista. Web. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/259249/consolidated-sales-of-L'Oréal-worldwide-by-geographic-zone/>

By showing this data, it can help understand that the consolidated sales growth of a company is affected by many factors, including its supply chain. This paper is mainly focusing on L'Oréal's supply chain management system. The reason of choosing this topic is because it is a very well-known cosmetics company in the world today. Even in the past popular articles, it was known that customers have been purchasing their products for over 100 years. This will demonstrate how they have changed over time to adapt to the fast-paced, technologically-driven society, which has led to changes in both the way they are run and supply chain management. The purpose of this study are:

1. To understand how L'Oréal manage to deal with its globalization and digital expansion.
2. To know how L'Oréal implements the distribution network and applications to online sales.
3. To understand ways to improve the supply chain coordination of L'Oréal.
4. The understand the transformation process of L'Oréal's supply chain system.
5. To analyze L'Oréal's supply chain strategy by integrating technology and data-driven practices.

The problems involved in this context is first, the company faces a complex challenge is the heavy turnover of products and launch cycles, multiple distribution channels and changing consumer tastes. Second, how does the company manage to have the effective coordination

in the supply chain to run effectively and responsively when it has 39 factories and 150 distribution centers worldwide to meet the 7 billion goods that consumers demand every year. Third, how to create a competitive advantage through supply chain management.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Understanding the supply chain

Supply chain are all stages involved directly or indirectly in fulfilling a customer request, with the objective to maximize overall value created (Chopra and Meindl, 2016). The supply chain in any business is made up of all the operations required to fulfill orders from customers. This includes the transfer of goods in both ways as well as information, assets, and goods from suppliers to manufacturers to distributors.

Achieving strategic fit and scope

A coordinated overall strategy is formed when the aims of the supply chain and competing strategies are aligned. This is known as strategic fit. To effectively implement these strategies, the various departments within a company need to effectively manage their resources and processes. In order to support the supply chain strategy, the overall supply chain design as well as the functions at each step must be coordinated. How strategic fit is achieved by:

1. Understanding the customer and supply chain uncertainty
2. Understanding supply chain capabilities
3. Achieving strategic fit

Supply chain drivers and metrics

Making decisions that make sense when taken as a whole and that match the circumstances is essential for successful decision-making. They shouldn't operate in opposition to one another, with one process optimized at the expense of others. A process with a close strategic fit and matching key process characteristics is more effective (Krajewski, 2022). Facilities are places where inventory is stored, assembled, or fabricated. It is production sites and storage sites. Determining where will the supply chain processes, such as its manufacturing and warehouses. In order to be in the competitive market, they must also make a competitive strategy, that is prioritizing efficiency and responsiveness. This is by considering its economies of scale, larger number of smaller facilities, manufacturing and warehousing methodology, and the overall trade off.

Inventory is raw materials, work-in-progress, finished goods within a supply chain. Inventory exists due to supply and demand imbalance. The source of cost and influence on responsiveness. If the company's priority is to gain responsiveness as the strategy, then the company can locate larger amounts of inventory closer to customers. Cost is therefore important, and a company can increase its efficiency by reducing its inventory. Different kinds of inventories, such as seasonal, safety, and cycle inventories.

Transportation is moving inventory from point to point in a supply chain. Faster transportation allows greater responsiveness but lower efficiency. If responsiveness is a strategic competitive priority, then faster transportation modes can provide greater responsiveness to customers who are willing to pay for it. So, using slower transportation can lower cost, and so it is important to consider both inventory and transportation to find the right balance. In order to achieve the ideal balance, it is crucial to take inventory and transportation into consideration. Slower transportation might thereby save costs. There are various kinds of combinations of transportation routes and modes, including pipeline, ship, rail, and air. Cost, delivery time, package size, and flexibility all vary. Businesses work to stop excessive product movement and material handling between processes, as these actions may damage products and lower their quality without providing much value to customers (Krajewski, 2022).

Information data and analysis may be the most important factors of supply chain performance as a part for the inventory, transportation, facilities. The connection between the various stages in the supply chain allows coordination to become more efficient and responsive all at once, hence all information must flow in the right pace.

Sourcing is a process of selecting and evaluating suppliers and management of supplier contracts (Manoj, 2022). The efficiency and responsiveness of a supply chain are both impacted by sourcing. Both in-house and outsourcing decisions are made. Overall, the trade-off is higher supply chain profitability. Pricing are related to the products and services that a company offers to the supply chain. It establishes how much a supply chain's customers will be charged. Demand and supply can be balanced with the help of the price strategy. Gaining more profit for the company is the overall trade-off.

Creating distribution networks and devising applications for online sales

Distribution is the process of moving and storing a product in a supply chain from the supplier stage to the customer stage. Distribution affects the profitability of a company by through its supply chain cost and customer experience. Distribution network selection can help the supply chain accomplish goals ranging from low cost to high responsiveness. The rapid increase in the usage of the Internet for business-to-business transactions as well as online purchasing has been one of the main drivers behind these shifts. (Christopher, 2023).

Although physical products take longer to supply than those found in retail stores, the impact of internet sales on customer service requires a quick response time to customers. There shouldn't be delay for information goods. Other than that, there are more product variety, so it is easier to offer larger selection. Product availability is increased through higher customer preference data and inventory grouping. Online platforms should place a high priority on convenience, improved access, customization, and consumer experience. Customers can be informed about promotions easily and quickly.

The impact of online sales on cost, is that the inventories and transportation cost will be low. Hence, reducing costs within the supply chain. The role of networks for the company is to

share demand, planning, and forecasting information in the supply chain. The disadvantage of utilizing online system is that there are additional costs to build and maintain the information infrastructure. This include ensuring that there are flexible distribution networks and a system that can connect the internet to the physical network that is already in use. Price, commoditization, and the importance of the product all influence the kind of distribution system that consumers prefer.

Role of sourcing in supply chain

The process through which businesses acquire products, services, raw materials, or other resources from suppliers in order to run their business is known as procurement. The complete range of business procedures needed to acquire products and services is known as sourcing (Jenkins, 2023). The most important choice for supply chain operations is whether to use in-house or outsource. An outsourcing business is a business that contracts with a third party to handle internal tasks. Outsourcing should be beneficial if it raises supply chain surplus without growing risks.

The process of leveling up supplier performance involves supplier rating and evaluation. The process of choosing a supplier involves using the results of supplier evaluation and scoring to determine qualified vendors. Suppliers and manufacturers can collaborate on the design of components for the finished product through design cooperation. The procedure through which a supplier ships goods in response to an order from a buyer is known as procurement. The goal of sourcing planning and analysis is to find ways to lower overall costs through analyzing how different suppliers and component categories cross-spend. Companies should identify the qualities that have the biggest impact on performance when developing a sourcing strategy and raise aims in those areas.

In order to make right choices about sourcing in the future, a company ought to constantly assess the performance of its suppliers and the amount it spends on procurement. Analyzing procurement cost by supplier and part can help to guarantee that the right economies of scale are achieved. Building a portfolio of suppliers with distinct advantages is an advantageous use for supplier performance analysis.

Transportation in a supply chain

Effective supply chain management depends on understanding how to choose the right form of transport for whatever freight moving (Sarder, 2021). The ground (truck, rail, pipeline); in the air; and through shipping (water) are the few types of transportations mode. In choosing whether to consider a transportation cost or inventory cost, it must be understood first that the choice of transportation mode is by considering the mode with higher transportation costs would results in significantly lower inventories or is necessary to maintain strategic level of responsiveness.

It is important to remember that one of the goals of supply chain management is to reduce or eliminate the buffers of inventory that exist between organizations in a chain through the

sharing of information regarding demand and current stock levels (Christopher, 2022). The efficient movement of goods includes 5 criteria: right price, right product, right condition, right time, and right place/person. As mentioned before regarding the different types of transportation modes, many companies are beginning to do intermodal transportation, meaning the company uses more than one type transporting goods, such as air to road or rail to water. This is to help cut transportation cost rather than using only one mode of transportation.

Coordination in the supply chain

Supply chain coordination improves if all stages of the chain take actions that are aligned and increase total supply chain surplus. Supply chain coordination requires each stage of the supply chain to share information and take into account the impact its actions have on other stages (Chopra, 2016). Supply chain's different stages affects the overall supply chain profits. There should not be misalignment of the company's supply chain objectives and individual objectives

Information technology and the supply chain

Coordination of inventory through information is what creates a coordinated supply chain. Including supply chain actors, such as suppliers, manufacturers and distributors, to ensure material flow and minimize costs to meet customer demand in the supply chain. That includes in operations, plan, and strategy. Therefore, it is important to manage inventory decisions in an integrated manner at all stages of the supply chain (Kaya, 2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Company Profile

L'Oréal, based in Clichy, Ile De France, France, produces and markets an extensive range of cosmetic items globally, catering to both women and men. Their offerings encompass makeup, perfumes, hair care, sun care, skincare, and coloring products. The company distributes its diverse array of brands—including Lancome, Giorgio Armani, Yves Saint Laurent, Kiehl's, Yue Sai, Maybelline New York, Redken, Kerastase, and Matrix—through a wide network that includes hair salons, mass-market retail, perfumeries, department stores, pharmacies, drugstores, branded retail outlets, and more. Besides physical stores, they also retail their products through various e-commerce platforms. With a global presence spanning North America, Latin America, Europe, Asia-Pacific, Africa, and the Middle East, L'Oréal serves diverse markets worldwide.

L'Oréal was founded in 1919 in Paris, France by chemist Eugene Schueller who created a hair dye called "Aureale". His strategy became successful; which soon afterward became L'Oréal. By the end of the 1920s, there were 40,000 hair salons in France alone and L'Oréal's new products captured the growing market. In 1928, the company made its first move toward

diversification, purchasing the soap company “Monsavon”.

By 1950s, an R&D (research-and-development) team of 100 chemists created further innovative products, including the first lightening tint, Imédia D, introduced in 1951, and the first coloring shampoo, Colorelle, introduced in 1955, which had an increasing demand for subtlety. The company advanced further into the field of skin care, entering into technological agreements with the company Vichy, in 1954 and became a part of the L'Oréal group in 1980.

Following a few years, the business expanded its globalization efforts, focusing especially on Hong Kong, Australia, New Zealand, and Japan. L'Oréal landed a technical help agreement with the Soviet Union in 1976. Thus, L'Oréal bought some cosmetics and hair care sectors during the 1970s, including Biotherm, Gemey, Ricils, Jeanne Piaubert, and Roja that year. In 1978, the two merged to form Garnier. Afterwards, it acquired a 53.4% controlling stake in Synthélabo, a pharmaceutical firm, and then bought Metabio-Joullie, a producer of medications, dietary, veterinary, and cosmetic products. Synthélabo was the result of the 1980 merger of Metabio-Joullie and Synthélabo. L'Oréal began investing in Marie-Claire Album and Interedi-Cosmopolitan in 1977 as part of its entry into the magazine publishing industry.

During the 1980s, Synthélabo enhanced its international status, setting up joint marketing affiliates in the United States and Britain (G.D. Searle), joint ventures in Japan (Fujisawa and Mitsubishi Kasei), Switzerland (Kramer), in 1982, and Italy (LIRCA). However, Synthélabo continued to report poor sales figures, so L'Oréal saw that the solution to Synthélabo's problems lay in extending its overseas sales, thereby offsetting unfavorable domestic pricing and reimbursement policies. By the end of the decade, profitability had improved and some promising new drugs were ready to be approved for marketing in the 1990s.

The R&D departments of L'Oréal, kept expanding steadily, and by 1984, there were 1,000 researchers working. One of the few anti-aging creams that succeeded was due to independent dermatologists discovering to be effective. Afterwards, the CEO of L'Oréal started building a multinational team of senior management, which allowed the business to quickly adapt to and take advantage of global market trends. Following the development of Lancôme Niosôme in 1986, L'Oréal applied the new technology to create a skin-care range for the mass market called Plentitude. When Plentitude was introduced in the United States, after being introduced in Europe and Australia in the late 1980s, it already held a 10% market share.

Luxury brands like Helena Rubenstein and Lancôme did quite well during the 1980s economic boom. L'Oréal also saw potential for additional profit growth in the U.S. market, which accounted for one-third of the global market. At the time, L'Oréal received only 5.5% of the earnings from its just-one U.S. agency, Cosmair Inc., despite having complete control over strategy, administration, and marketing in this region. One benefit of this system

for L'Oréal was protection against high marketing costs and the depreciation of the US dollar. Cosmoair handled over \$1 billion in sales, giving the company the autonomy to introduce new products that could then be distributed to L'Oréal affiliates across the globe.

L'Oréal formed a joint venture called Soreal with the Russian chemical business Mosbytchim, making it one of the first Western corporations to establish an operation in the former Soviet Union. To create about 40 million pieces of deodorant, perfume, shampoos, and hair sprays yearly, L'Oréal committed \$50 million in the initiative. In 1992, there were only 100 Soreal stores in Moscow and 10 more around Russia that carried the brand's products. Because banks either failed or were not used to working with Western enterprises, hard currency was hard to come by. Soreal developed a women's fragrance called Maroussia, which was shipped to Western Europe in return for the machinery and supplies needed to improve production.

During this time, L'Oréal's organizational structure remained the same, with the company being a federation of competitive enterprises that were split into five divisions and had 147 manufacturing and distribution facilities globally. The only things that were centralized were overall management control and research and development facilities. When Bettencourt left her corporate role in 1990, and concern about what would happen to L'Oréal ensued. The problem piqued the interest of the French authorities. Prior to 1994, agreements made by the French government prohibited foreigners from acquiring control of French firms. Even yet, by 2001 Bettencourt retained control over her stake in the company; if she chose to sell, Nestlé would have an advantage on the sale.

Consumers are beginning to be more environmentally aware, as a big company, L'Oreal was expected to also care for the environment, that includes the product's safety by avoiding in using chlorofluorocarbons (harmful chemical for the ozone layer of the planet). Other than that, it is also concerning about the animal protection, of stopping in using animal testing by 1989.

As L'Oréal entered the mid-1990s, the company had a tight competitor called Proctor & Gamble and Unilever for worldwide domination of the mass cosmetic and fragrance markets. However, L'Oréal wants to remain as market leader, hence they increased their advertising budget by 50% , and invented a new reputation for its cosmetics. By repackaging its merchandise and making display cases, customer found it efficient because it was more accessible and user-friendly. The following year, they purchased Maybelline brand for \$600 million. In 1996 the U.S. market, merged its hair care and cosmetics division under one supervision. Then they also created Garnier hair care brand.

Overview Of L'Oréal's Supply Chain

L'Oréal's global strategy recognizes globalization while keeping its focus on its consumer. The supply chain utilized by this company is customer-centric (Howlett, 2018). The company's approach is acquiring brands that have been created locally or regionally then rapidly expand them to a global level. With a global market and a flexible supply chain

strategy to continuously adjust to customer needs, the customer is the primary focus. The ability to provide the same level of cost, quality, and customer service despite fluctuations in supply and demand is known as agility.

The table shows L’Oreal’s performance compared to the industry’s average growth, but outperforming the average on operating margin, inventory turns, ROI capital, market cap, price to tangible book. Showing that L’Oreal’s position is ranked second. This shows what balanced portfolio of a supply chain revolution drive.

Performance and Improvement (2010-2017): Personal Products

Company	Growth	Operating Margin	Inventory Turns	Return on Invested Capital	Market Cap (000,000)	Price to Tangible Book Value	Supply Chain Index Rank
Avon Products	-6.6%	0.06	3.7	-6.9%	\$5,335	49.5	12
Beiersdorf	0.2%	0.13	3.3	15.4%	\$22,175	4.6	3
CCA Industries	-11.6%	-0.02	2.6	-12.3%	\$26	2.1	17
Coty	14.3%	0.03	2.9	-0.1%	\$10,053	-2.9	4
Estee Lauder	6.3%	0.14	1.8	20.5%	\$28,277	15.2	4
Henkel AG & Company *WINNER*	2.4%	0.14	5.5	11.8%	\$42,791	-3.5	8
Herbalife Ltd	9.0%	0.14	2.6	34.7%	\$5,043	-6.9	10
Inter Parfums	5.7%	0.16	1.8	10.0%	\$839	4.1	9
Kao Corporation	-0.6%	0.10	4.4	11.0%	\$20,010	4.6	1
L’Oreal *WINNER*	2.6%	0.17	3.0	14.6%	\$91,398	6.7	2
Natures Sunshine Products	0.1%	0.05	2.2	7.3%	\$232	2.1	11
Nu Skin Enterprises	8.8%	0.14	2.1	21.2%	\$3,267	6.3	12
Ocean Bio-Chem Inc.	5.8%	0.09	2.5	10.0%	\$26	1.5	16
Oriflame Cosmetics SA	-3.5%	0.10	2.1	15.1%	\$1,371	9.6	15
PZ Cussons PLC	-2.4%	0.11	3.3	9.7%	\$1,901	14.2	7
Revlon Inc	10.1%	0.11	3.5	15.2%	\$1,170	-0.9	12
Shiseido Co Ltd	4.8%	0.06	2.1	3.9%	\$8,889	5.2	4
Average	2.7%	0.10	2.9	10.6%	\$9,463	3.9	

Source: Supply Chain Insights 2018, Derived from YCharts; Showing average over time period; Supply Chain Index Rank = Based on average ranking within industry of Balance (Return on Invested Capital & Revenue Growth Vector Trajectory), Strength (Inventory Turns & Operating Margin Vector Trajectory) and Resiliency (Inventory Turns & Operating Margin Mean Distance; low score = better); Averages exclude outliers for purposes of Supply Chains to Admire calculations

Source: Supply Chain Shaman. (2018). L’Oréal: A Case Study in Supply Chain Excellence. <https://www.supplychainshaman.com/loreal-a-case-study-in-supply-chain-excellence/>

L’Oréal had a digital transformation in its operations, so they had to significantly adjusted due to digital transformation, and this led to challenges for its value proposition, approach, and culture (Seifert, R. W. & Markoff, R, 2022). They focused more on digital as a result of anticipating shifts in demand. For instance, over 40% of the company's business in China is conducted through e-commerce. In 2017, the company had a 34% increase in worldwide e-commerce, and it anticipates that trend to continue. This is changing L’Oréal's approach to performing business. These days, L’Oréal spends more than 38% of its advertising budget on digital. The supply chain team collaborates closely with the digital marketing teams to guarantee alignment as this is how the company increases the markets.

The company recognizes customer preferences to adapt and reposition its product line to offer customized options for purchase at any time and from any location. As a result, the business now has a hyper-connected relationship with the end user. Additionally, in order to

satisfy environmentally conscious consumers, the business has created a system for evaluating the social and environmental benefits of every new product it releases. A conceptualized product won't be released if its performance falls short of that of a comparable product that has already been released. This approach has fundamentally shifted L'Oréal's response to the market (Howlett, 2018).

L'Oréal constantly rethinks network optimization and physical distribution to adapt to changing consumer preferences. This is a continuing, active process. Because of the emphasis on e-Commerce and the resulting smaller order sizes, detailed picking is becoming a growing trend. In the past few decades, the hair salon channel has primarily used detail-picking orders for luxury products. Selecting "each" represents the entire catalog for all eight distribution channels.

Source: Cecere, L. (2019). L'oreal Presentation from the Supply Chain Insights Global Summit 2018. <https://www.slideshare.net/loracecere/loreal-presentation-from-the-supply-chain-insights-global-summit-2018>

François-Régis's focus is defining agility in operations through their Operations 4.0 strategy. This phrase refers to a shift in how a company operates, specifically in manufacturing, supply chain, and global operations, aligning with the pace and direction of business evolution and consumer behavior. The company's strategy is by analyzing consumer requirements and then integrating manufacturing technologies like virtual reality, simulation, machine learning, and 3D printing. As the company moved from limited data availability to having ample data stored at lower costs, the emphasis changed from acquiring data to leveraging data for valuable insights (Tronvoll, 2020).

L'Oréal changed how product prototypes are created, that is through 3D printing. They are more flexible and allows smaller production runs, this reduced manufacturing expenses, and quicker production cycles compared to conventional methods. The priority is accelerating time-to-market to support growth plans. 3D printing drastically reduced the development cycle from 60 days for initial models, which were costly, to just 15 days.

In the company's industry, compatibility testing of the formulation and packaging is essential

prior to the release of a new product. For instance, hazardous leaks from the chemical reaction between the product formula and aerosol cans. In order to provide technical skills for discovering potential interactions based only on artificial intelligence and machine learning, L'Oréal partnered with IBM. The time-to-market has been significantly shortened by this technology, since compatibility checks can take up to six months.

Understanding the supply chain

Based on HKT Consultant (2021), the material is distributed by the company through 23 clearing and forwarding agents (C&FA), one in each state. C&FAs offer facilities for storage, billing, and delivery. L'Oréal India benefits from consignment sales through C&FA by avoiding double taxation on interstate sales, introducing order size flexibility, and improving transportation efficiency. At the moment, transportation expenses account for less than 2% of net sales. The duration of the stocks at C&FAs, dealers, and retailers are, respectively, 60 days, 30 days, and 30-90 days.

At L'Oréal India, the logistics cost breakdown is 1.5% for freight, 0.7% for warehousing, and 0.3% for overheads, for a total of 2.5%, which is within the FMCG industry standards. The payment receivable is 10 days on average. There are 455 consumer products, 239 professional products, and 31 active cosmetics at the 725 SKU level. There are 200 fast-moving SKUs at any given time. The company uses a flexible ordering system that distributes twice a week to once a month through CFA.

Fig. 1 Logistics process

Fig. 2 Distribution flow

Source: HKT Consultant. (2021). L’Oreal – Improvising Supply Chain Performance. <https://phantran.net/loreal-improvising-supply-chain-performance/>

The L’Oreal’s India flow chart shown above, it can be explained that the procurement planning scheduling for imported in stock keeping unit (SKU) is based on the sales forecast for both domestic and international markets. The order quantity is managed by considering the 75 days lead time for certain class items, then 60 days for other items, and deducting the stocks leads to transit of 23 warehouses. Due to supply chain optimization activities, this corporation modified its policy of maintaining two months' worth of stock—one month at the national warehouse and one month at the CFAs—resulting in a stock cover of only roughly 40 days. This was due to the implementation of effective distribution strategies that prevented shortages. The department was able to secure a reduction of 11.5% in freight prices by renegotiating rates with transporters, made possible by a significant rise in volumes. The rise in sales volume, which resulted in larger manufacturing batch sizes and lower production costs and greater margins, was another factor in the total decrease in operating expenses.

Achieving Strategic Fit and Scope of L'Oréal

There are three steps to achieving strategic fit. First, understanding the customer and supply chain uncertainty. Second, understanding the supply chain. Third, achieving strategic fit. L'Oréal must ensure that all functions maintain consistent strategies that support the competitive strategy. They use intraoperation scope, meaning they minimize local cost view. L'Oréal's strategic fit can be analyzed through understanding the diverse demand of consumers around the world. L'Oréal achieves strategic fit through establishing six R&D centers worldwide, catering to the unique needs of key markets like the US, Japan, Brazil, China, India, and South Africa. This allows for the development of products with localized formulas and ingredients. So, L'Oréal manufactures and distributes its products regionally, ensuring faster delivery times and cultural appropriateness.

L'Oréal has a wide range of consumers through its extensive portfolio of brands across various price points and categories, from luxury offerings like Lancôme to mass-market brands like Garnier. They also invest heavily in R&D, constantly developing new products and technologies that cater to specific consumer needs and preferences. For example, the company has launched hair care products specifically formulated for different hair types and textures. Offering customized beauty solutions like hair color recommendations and skincare routines based on individual needs and preferences. Hence, L'Oréal's strategic fit is strong. Its focus on understanding and catering to diverse consumer needs, coupled with its commitment to innovation and sustainability, positions the company well for continued growth in the global beauty market.

Supply Chain Drivers and Metrics in L'Oréal

Facilities

Warehouse management plays a crucial role in the supply chain of L'Oréal. Efficient management of warehouses is essential to ensure smooth operations and timely delivery of products. The company focuses on optimizing warehouse processes and implementing advanced technologies to enhance productivity and reduce costs. Key metrics used to measure warehouse management performance include order fulfillment rate, accuracy of picking and packing, cycle time, and inventory turnover. L'Oréal also emphasizes on maintaining high levels of stock accuracy to avoid stockouts and overstocking. By continuously improving warehouse management practices, L'Oréal is able to streamline its supply chain and meet customer demands effectively.

Production facilities in L'Oréal's supply chain management continually improves and optimize their production facilities, L'Oréal aims to enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and increase overall productivity. This involves utilizing advanced technologies and lean manufacturing principles to streamline processes, minimize waste, and ensure high-quality output. Additionally, L'Oréal focuses on optimizing production capacity and flexibility to meet changing demand and market conditions. By continuously monitoring and analyzing

metrics related to production facilities, such as equipment utilization, cycle times, and downtime, L'Oréal can identify areas for improvement and implement strategic initiatives to optimize their production facilities effectively.

In the context of supply chain drivers and metrics in L'Oréal, the focus is on distribution center efficiency. This aspect is crucial for streamlining the flow of products and optimizing the overall supply chain operations. By enhancing distribution center efficiency, L'Oréal can effectively manage inventory levels, reduce costs, and improve customer service. This involves implementing advanced warehouse management systems, optimizing layout and space utilization, and leveraging technology for real-time visibility and data analytics. Additionally, L'Oréal aims to enhance transportation efficiency through freight cost optimization, monitoring carrier performance, and reducing delivery lead times. These efforts contribute to improving overall supply chain performance and supporting L'Oréal's commitment to delivering high-quality products to its customers efficiently and effectively.

Inventory

L'Oréal's commitment to lean inventory practices helps balance maintaining product availability and reducing excess stock (Dfreight, 2023). The company ensure product availability by providing real-time visibility into inventory levels throughout its distribution network, at the time and location that consumers require them. Effective inventory control also enables L'Oréal to react quickly to new product releases and shifting consumer needs. The company supports in incorporating advanced technologies in order to maximize accuracy and efficiency in its supply chain processes, from using Internet of Things (IoT) sensors for real-time inventory tracking to using artificial intelligence for demand forecasting. So, lean inventory management should always balance supply, demand, and productive resources; integrate information technologies; allow multiple manufacturing units and distribution spread across different locations or regions; and allow each production process to operate with maximum efficiency (Sobreiro, 2017).

Transportation

L'Oreal discovered that cutting back on air travel has a major effect on lowering carbon emissions. Following a study of the most popular forms of transportation, L'Oreal made a commitment to cut emissions by 25% from supply chain transportation by the year 2030. According to Le Tourneau, the corporation has shifted to only employing alternative fuel-powered trucks in Paris. By including sustainable transportation in its supplier selection criteria, cutting back on air travel, moving as much cargo as possible to rail and ship modes, and utilizing alternative vehicles in urban areas, the company will be able to meet its objectives.

Truck and air freight dominated L'Oreal's emissions in 2017
% of total CO2 emissions by mode of transportation

Source: Cosgrove, M. (2018). Want a more sustainable supply chain? L'Oreal says avoid air freight. <https://www.supplychaindive.com/news/Why-L-Oreal-avoids-air-freight-emissions/538652/>

The chart above shows that air freight produces more carbon emission than sea freight and rail freight. In addition, trucks and rails has similar contribution in emissions, smaller trucks and vans that are used to move goods in busy cities contribute the most carbon, second to air freight. So, L'Oreal has adjusted its supply chain by increasing efficiency and execution while moving as much of its volume to more environmentally friendly modes of transportation. The reduction in emissions is not permanent. Sometimes, organizations faces regression. Internal buy-in is crucial when changing to alternative fuels because they are difficult to maintain (Cosgrove, 2018).

Information

The supply chain transformation to digital was able to increase transparency, meaning consumers can now obtain all the product information they require to make well-informed choices, from the location and date of manufacture to the source information of ingredients, all due to technology such as QR Codes. This strategy even includes using real-time technologies for package tracking. Employees can access customer service and purchase histories, order status updates, and real-time activity updates all from a single dashboard. For example, a customer can place an online order for Lancôme Absolu Soft Cream. However, the order had an error due to supply chain problems, which automatically opens a case and assigns it to an employee. The employee can proactively submit a "reship" order before the customer is even aware of the problem, since the product and shipment details are already stored in the system. This eliminates the need for brands to follow up or get in touch with customers in order to guarantee that things will reach them on time.

Sourcing

L'Oréal outsourced its transportation to address challenges in holding vendors accountable for inbound transportation requirements. The company chose the Ultra ship TMS flagship solution to automate its routing guide and improve visibility. The company also aimed to improve business unit collaboration and pool purchasing leverage volume for cost savings and service improvements. L'Oréal had a TMS in place to oversee outbound transport but needed to gain control over inbound raw material flow to its manufacturers. The company revamped the process by starting at the top to improve the flow of components and raw materials into manufacturing facilities.

Pricing

Cost-to-serve analysis allows the company to evaluate the true cost associated with serving different customers and channels. By analyzing the cost-to-serve, L'Oréal can identify areas for cost reduction and operational efficiency improvements. This analysis helps in determining the profitability of various products, customers, and distribution channels, enabling the company to make informed decisions regarding pricing, sourcing, and resource allocation. Ultimately, the cost-to-serve analysis plays a significant role in optimizing L'Oréal's supply chain operations and ensuring that the company maximizes its profitability while meeting customer demands.

Price optimization strategies in L'Oréal play a crucial role in maximizing profitability and ensuring competitiveness in the market. The company employs various tactics to optimize prices, such as dynamic pricing, value-based pricing, and promotional pricing. Dynamic pricing allows L'Oréal to adjust prices in real-time based on factors like demand, competitor prices, and customer preferences. Value-based pricing focuses on capturing the perceived value of products and aligning prices accordingly. Promotional pricing strategies involve offering discounts and deals to attract customers and drive sales. By implementing these price optimization strategies, L'Oréal effectively balances profitability and customer satisfaction, contributing to its overall supply chain performance.

Designing L'Oréal's Distribution Networks and Applications to Online Sales

L'Oréal's distribution network requires a supply chain that is evolving as digital technology, this is to create a service that is quick to response for customer satisfaction. This creates a challenge of satisfying both online and offline stores that is facing challenges, such as more demand in e-commerce, product personalization and management of products data, and choosing delivery modes with assurance of rapidness, safety and quality. According to Pymnts, one of the key factors contributing to L'Oréal's excellent 2021 was its 25.7% growth in e-commerce. The firm said that sales increased by 16.1% overall in 2021, which was double the industry average at 32.28 billion euros (\$36.82 billion). 28.9% of L'Oréal's total sales came from its increase in eCommerce, the firm said in its earnings report. They are also carrying out the omnichannel strategy's integrated point of sale digitalization at the same time. In addition to investing in data and artificial intelligence and forming strategic alliances

like Verily (health company), the Beauty Tech transformation is being pursued to better understand and define the aging mechanisms of skin and hair. For the purpose of investing in its brands and boosting their attractiveness, so L'Oréal also had to manage its cost management strategically.

Role Of Sourcing in L'Oréal's Supply Chain

L'Oréal outsources its transportation, this is because they recognized a challenge with holding vendors complaint to inbound transportation requirements. Hence, L'Oréal in the USA chose Elmwood Park, N.J. based Ultra ship TMS flagship solution to help automate its routing guide and attain greater visibility. The firm discovered that in order to reduce costs and enhance services, business groups inside the organization needed to collaborate more closely and combine their purchasing power.

To manage outbound transportation from distribution centers to customers, L'Oréal used a TMS. However, it required more control over the flow of incoming raw materials to its manufacturing facilities. Instead of mentioning L'Oréal's recommended carriers, vendors have chosen their own. The business made the decision to start at the top in order to redesign the procedure. This strategy was important in enhancing the flow of raw materials and components into production plants.

1. **Compliance:** To convey appropriate transportation instructions to suppliers. The cost savings from simply holding vendors and suppliers more accountable have been significant.
2. **Mode selection:** Shipments weighing 20,000 pounds should move truckload, not LTL. The system, not the supplier, now dictates mode.
3. **Optimization:** Manufacturers have the tools to go back to suppliers and figure out how to ship to us more efficiently. The supply chain is revised by delivering more accurate lead times. This allows our suppliers to pool shipments, and have freight ready to build full truckloads.

The TMS roll-out by L'Oréal was both necessary and advantageous, considering the direction the market was taking. The goal for businesses is to connect the connections in the chain, integrate the TMS with any existing warehouse or transportation management system, and use it as a tool for the supply chain. The manufacturer still utilizes different transportation management systems to handle incoming and outgoing shipments, despite having been able to improve inter-plant transportation efficiency between manufacturing sites and distribution centers. It will eventually transition to a system that combines the two. In this manner, it can optimize outward movements using inbound freight data. After a TMS is fully operational, carrier and customer cooperation is virtually limitless. Reacting to variable demand and marrying marketing and logistics efforts requires a great deal of collaboration. Personal care product manufacturers can choose from a wealth of resources and strategies, but these four tools of the trade are especially important.

1. Inbound Logistics—Controlling inbound transportation and product flow at each pivot in the supply chain—from manufacturing plants to distribution facilities to retail stores—helps businesses pull inventory to demand. Capturing demand signals from the point of sale, then sharing this information with marketing, logistics, and service providers upstream in the supply chain, enhances visibility, grows collaboration, and increases flexibility and economy.
2. Freight Consolidation—SKU variability and differing carton sizes, multi-channel business requirements, and varying transportation demands make freight consolidation a must for cosmetics companies. From locating inventory in centralized DCs to controlling inbound transportation and pooling shipments, manufacturers can improve asset utilization and freight spend.
3. Packaging—Packaging is an executable solution for the health and beauty industry. It's a means of conveying information and appeal to a consumer, and reducing material footprint has an impact on load optimization and transportation needs. Marketing and logistics each have a hand in engineering packaging requirements, which can increase communication and collaboration in countless other ways.

Importance of transportation In L'Oréal's Supply Chain

In terms of fighting climate change, and in order to align our greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, they have set the ambitious goal for 2030 of cutting these emissions, including those related to transport, by 50% per finished product compared with 2016 levels. To achieve this, our Supply Chain teams, who are responsible for getting our products from their manufacturing site to consumers, are innovating and reinventing transportation. A key component in our drive to cut GHG emissions is to rethink product transportation:

- Over long distances, by turning to alternative transportation methods, such as sea and rail freight, and less polluting vehicles, including trucks powered by liquefied natural gas (LNG) and, in the future, hydrogen.
- Over short distances and the “last mile,” through the use of less polluting vehicles, including electric vehicles, LNG-powered vehicles, and zero-emission alternatives such as bicycles.

The Whistle project illustrates how the Group is switching to alternative transportation choices. Set up by L'Oréal USA, this initiative prioritizes rail freight over road transportation wherever possible, helping to bring down transportation costs as well as CO₂ emissions. In Shanghai, L'Oréal China has been engaged since 2019 in an initiative to gradually lower delivery-related GHG emissions. Today, 70% of downtown deliveries are done using electric, biofuel or LNG vehicles. The plan now is to use this initiative in L'Oréal China's other cities.

By collecting data, L'Oréal can better anticipate consumers' needs and expectations, as well as changing approaches to consumption itself. These efforts are also being taken forward

through upstream collaboration within the Group aimed at integrating transportation issues in discussions around new-product launches. The goal is to be more agile and responsive, ensuring that our products and services are available when and where consumers want them, while at the same time reducing our carbon footprint. In 2020, for example, L'Oréal Luxe sought to reduce CO₂ emissions by anticipating production and distribution for its gift box range. After being produced in Europe, these boxes are distributed all over the world for the year-end holidays, which adds the challenge of ensuring on-time delivery. These efforts to anticipate and collaborate, both inside the Group and with partners, paid off, allowing us to half our CO₂ emissions linked to air transport, notably by using sea freight.

Coordination In the Supply Chain of L'Oréal

According to Dufлот (2014) analysis, the bullwhip effect is responsible for the cancellation of orders as the volume seen by L'Oréal cannot always be fulfilled. Production and stock amongst the clients are affected by this amplification when it is aggregated at the brand and category levels. Inaccurate forecasts might have two causes. If the entire demand must be met and the final buyer has the option to purchase another product, either the products are canceled or back ordered, resulting in major losses as the unsold goods are moving to the competition. In contrast, ineffective forecast accuracy may result from overestimating the amounts needed, which raises the holding costs. However, the warehouse's capacity can be balanced by sharing it with three other countries, and any excess inventory may be purchased or redistributed by another L'Oréal subsidiary

At the beginning of a sourcing process, it is important to analyze the suppliers before creating long term relationships. Every supplier should be treated fairly, meaning that the company provides the same information and to ensure that there is internal coordination to make sure the supplier will be selected on objective and verified information. In reality, this function is often performed by the purchasing department. L'Oréal implements intelligent product movement to increase filling operations' flexibility for cosmetics.

Previously, the production of make-up foundations in Caudry consisted of multiple machines from different vendors that were connected through conveyor systems and product buffers. However, due to its lack of flexibility, L'Oréal decided on a fundamental realignment by implementing an innovative line that would accommodate the production of all formats combined with speedy changeover capabilities and be available at optimized manufacturing costs. The new line, called Agile F24, the system specifications were developed in cooperation with machine builder Secad. Following an evaluation, the parties decided to replace the existing machines with a single line based on the intelligent transport system XTS (Beckhoff, 2020).

Hence, L'Oréal utilizes smart product transportation to enhance the adaptability of cosmetic filling processes. The system L'Oréal uses for production is from Beckhoff's XTS (eXtended Transport System), it uses five machines for a single production line combined that reduces footprint by 30%. They manufacture makeup goods for their Division Luxe in their Caudry

plant. Already, three of the production lines are built includes the new Agile F24 filling and capping line, which supports the company's aim to improve the agility of its manufacturing operations by enabling quick format changes with an equal increase in output (Beckhoff, 2020).

Prior to the filling operation, a handling robot removes the empty containers and packs them into pucks (transport containers) that are attached to the XTS movers and match the specific product format. Leading cosmetics manufacturer L'Oréal set a strategic goal to increase the speed of the company's production processes in response to trends like growing individualization and smaller production quantities, which bring challenges, particularly in the expanding luxury market. In this way, L'Oréal will be able to meet the increasing demand for luxury cosmetics in the future without having to expand its production floor area. The resulting investment security is also protected by another key benefit of the XTS, which is increased flexibility. Through the software-based control with TwinCAT, the XTS can switch between different product variants. This capability makes it possible to process different single lines instead of using several machines. Another benefit is the XTS allows to switch to another color within seconds (reducing lot sizes and meet changes from customers). The centralized control principle of the XTS system makes operation, and quality management tasks in particular, much easier. These include sample removal, running the line empty if necessary and check weighing. All these tasks are fully automated including RFID support (Beckhoff, 2020).

Other than XTS, they also implemented in TwinCAT for automation tasks, which created a centralized control panel for the whole system. Using PLC software and integrated axis control, cloud connectivity and other machine functions. With the help of XTS and PC-based control, the production line is flexible, can meet high quality requirements and new consumer expectations. Operators can control the entire process including all quality checks and sampling on their own and execute format changeovers quickly and easily.

L'Oréal's Information Technology and its Supply Chain

The IT division in L'Oreal are the innovation facilitators. They carry out the task of designing and creating solutions for high performance through new strategies in designing their different websites until algorithms in forecasting new trends. The company's leading team is leaning towards a digitalized and connected future of e-commerce, IT retail, AI, e-marketing, and cybersecurity. In information technology, there are systems that can be applied to a company, one of which that L'Oréal selects is from International Business Machines Corporation. It is called the IBM PureSystems, used to provide a new private cloud-based, smarter computing infrastructure for its operations in Uruguay. This system was able to make the company able to reduce its power consumption and overall size of its IT infrastructure (IBM, 2023). L'Oréal of Uruguay decided to use this system to modernize their IT environment that would be able to have a cloud-ready and secure infrastructure that is able to meet the company's growth strategy demand.

IBM also has PureFlex system that helps L’Oreal with the IT backbone needed to expand operations into the cloud and deliver the latest personalized offering for customers. So, since L’Oréal Uruguay are more focused in producing the highest quality goods and services, the IBM PureFlex was able to improve their level of availability and continue growth plans. The system made it more flexible and simpler for the IT management, and reduced energy consumption and total space of infrastructure, which are two key elements in the current competitive landscape. All of L’Oréal’s computing, storage, network, virtualization, and management functions are combined into PureFlex, a single system that is meant to identify infrastructure requirements and maximize resources. To further increase the effectiveness of IT systems, this solution also consists of integrated patterns of knowledge that are intended to automate and optimize the implementation and maintenance of their workloads.

CONCLUSION

L’Oréal’s supply chain manages and enhances both the flow of information in digital and physical products from suppliers to sales points. The company boasts an efficient global, and domestic management structure. It fosters a culture of entrepreneurship within regions, urging each to understand its customers and encouraging collaboration between supply chain teams and commercial or digital marketing teams. This model is recognized as one of the most effective in regional and global governance studies. L’Oréal’s supply chain evolves rapidly, keeping pace with digital advancements. The goal is to ensure complete customer satisfaction, whether in-store or online, addressing challenges like the rise of e-commerce, personalized products, and diverse delivery methods—all without compromising on quality, speed, or safety.

REFERENCES

Advameg. (n.d.). L’Oréal SA - Company Profile, Information, Business Description, History, Background Information on L’Oréal SA <https://www.referenceforbusiness.com/history2/74/L-Or-al-SA.html>

Beckhoff. (2020). L’Oréal uses intelligent product transport to improve the flexibility in cosmetics filling operations. <https://www.beckhoff.com/en-au/company/news/l-oreal-uses-intelligent-product-transport-to-improve-the-flexibility-in-cosmetics-filling-operations.html>

Cosgrove, M. (2018). Want a more sustainable supply chain? L’Oreal says avoid air freight. <https://www.supplychaindive.com/news/Why-L-Oreal-avoids-air-freight-emissions/538652/>

Christopher, M. (2023). Logistics & Supply Chain Management. Sixth Edition p. 56

Chen, X., Yan, H. (2021). L’Oréal Group Strategic Analysis and Recommendations. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/90ed/401874e7b460fc8122605ee4185d3c6a90e9.pdf>

Chopra, S., Meindl, P. (2016). Supply Chain Management Strategy, Planning, and Operation sixth edition

- CGT. (2013). L'Oréal Enhances IT Infrastructure with IBM. <https://consumergoods.com/loreal-enhances-it-infrastructure-ibm>
- Dfreight. (2023). An Insight into L'Oréal Supply Chain Strategy.
- Duflot, L. (2014). Collaboration and Information Sharing toward forecasting A case study at L'Oréal Sverige AB. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:730873/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Global Data. (n.d.). L'Oréal SA: Overview. <https://www.globaldata.com/company-profile/l-oreal-sa/>
- HKT Consultant. (2021). L'Oreal – Improvising Supply Chain Performance. <https://phantran.net/loreal-improvising-supply-chain-performance/>
- Howarth, J. (2023). The Ultimate List of Beauty Industry Stats (2023). <https://explodingtopics.com/blog/beauty-industry-stats>
- Howlett, D. (2018). L'Oréal's CX - Baking In The Supply Chain Elements. <https://diginomica.com/loreal-cx-baking-in-the-supply-chain-elements>
- Jenkins, A. (2023). What Is Procurement? Types, Processes & Technology. <https://www.netsuite.com/portal/resource/articles/accounting/procurement.shtml>
- Kaya, O. (2020). Supply Chain Management. pp.107-135
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/356085653_Inventory_Management_in_Supply_Chains
- L'Oréal Operations. (n.d.). The Way We Work with Our Suppliers. <https://www.L'Oréal.com/-/media/project/L'Oréal/brand-sites/corp/master/lcorp/documents-media/publications/the-way-we-work-with-our-suppliers.pdf?rev=6ebd77fed23349379da3d66b9fe36e83>
- L'Oréal Groupe. (n.d.). L'Oréal Embraces Green Transportation to Meet Environmental Challenges. <https://www.L'Oréal.com/en/articles/commitments/green-transportation/>
- L'Oréal Groupe. (n.d.). Our History. <https://www.loreal.com/en/group/culture-and-heritage/l-oreal-history/>
- L'Oréal Groupe. (n.d.). L'Oréal's Supply Chain Ranked 9th Worldwide And 4th In Consumer Products Industry <https://www.loreal.com/en/news/commitments/loreal-ranked-4th-worldwide-for-its-supply-chain/>
- Martínez-Peláez, R.; Ochoa-Brust, A.; Rivera, S.; Félix, V.G.; Ostos, R.; Brito, H.; Félix, R.A.; Mena, L.J. (2023). Role of Digital Transformation for Achieving Sustainability: Mediated Role of Stakeholders, Key Capabilities, and Technology. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151411221>
- Medium. (2020). Transforming L'Oréal Supply Chain? A fascinating

challenge! <https://beautytmr.medium.com/transforming-lor%C3%A9al-supply-chain-a-fascinating-challenge-95b1ae0c32cb>

Petruzzi, D. (2021). Consolidated sales of L'Oréal worldwide from 2010 to 2020, by geographic zone. Statista. Web. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/259249/consolidated-sales-of-L'Oréal-worldwide-by-geographic-zone/>

Sales Force. (n.d.). L'Oréal creates unique beauty experiences with a data-driven approach. <https://www.salesforce.com/resources/customer-stories/loreal-data-unique-beauty-experiences/>

Soares, T. D. L. V. A. D. M., Silva, B. B. L. D. (2012). Assessing The Strategy Of Firms That Compete Globally In Alliances In The Cosmetics Industry: The Case Of L'oréal In Latin America. <https://virtusinterpress.org/IMG/pdf/T-Diana-L-van-Aduard-de-Macedo-Soares-Barbara-Braga-Lyra-da-Silva-paper.pdf>

Seifert, R.W., Markoff, R. (2022). L'Oréal: The Beauty Of Supply Chain Digitalization. <https://www.imd.org/research-knowledge/supply-chain/case-studies/l-oral-the-beauty-of-supply-chain-digitalization/>

Sobreiro, V. A., Kimura, H., Moori, R. (2017). A lean inventory management model as a competitive strategy analysis tool: implications for sustainability. Latin American J of Management for Sustainable Development. DOI: [10.1504/LAJMSD.2017.10010481](https://doi.org/10.1504/LAJMSD.2017.10010481)

Supply Chain Shaman. (2018). L'Oréal: A Case Study in Supply Chain Excellence. <https://www.supplychainshaman.com/loreal-a-case-study-in-supply-chain-excellence/>

Tronvolla, B., Sklyar A., Sörhammar, D., Kowalkowski, C. (2020). Transformational shifts through digital servitization. Industrial Marketing Management. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2020.02.005>

Sarder, MD. (2021). Logistics Transportation Systems [https://ftp.idu.ac.id/wp-content/uploads/ebook/ip/LOGISTIK%20TRANSPOTASI/Logistics%20Transportation%20S%20ystems%20by%20MD%20Sarder%20\(z-lib.org\).pdf](https://ftp.idu.ac.id/wp-content/uploads/ebook/ip/LOGISTIK%20TRANSPOTASI/Logistics%20Transportation%20S%20ystems%20by%20MD%20Sarder%20(z-lib.org).pdf)